

SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS

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Annotation: Numerous studies have confirmed that the development of strength properties in track and field athletes is of fundamental importance for the overall athletic performance. In this regard, it is important to include in the educational and training process such types of physical activity that, along with the development of the above mentioned qualities, would also contribute to the strengthening and improvement of the cardiorespiratory system of young people.

Key words: students, athletics, sprint, higher education institution, special physical training.

Introduction. As practice shows, the educational and training process of preparing athletes from non-core higher education institutions is carried out in conditions of insufficient equipment and using ineffective teaching methods. This task is especially acute in complex coordination types of athletics, which significantly reduces the effectiveness of the learning process and interest in the educational and training process [3, 4].

Auxiliary equipment, simulators and devices at the current stage of the development of the sport make it possible to solve educational problems with great success, to develop the necessary skills and abilities in track and field athletes, to work fruitfully on the development of physical qualities, and to implement tasks related to the prevention of injuries and the recovery of athletes [1, 2].

In the educational and training process of training young athletes in sprint running, one cannot do without speed-strength exercises. In practice, training devices or weight-bearing exercises are usually used for this purpose [4, 5, 7]. Increasing the level of maximum anaerobic power is possible through the use of special jumping exercises on stairs in the training process. It has been proven that track and field athletes specializing in short-distance running can effectively replace traditional speed-strength exercises, most often used in sports training during classes in the gym, with a set of jumping exercises [6, 8].

In order to enhance the positive effect, it is recommended to use such a set of jumping exercises 2 times a week for 3-5 series during the entire training period [2, 7, 8]. The use of a set of special jumping exercises on stairs in the educational and training process of training student athletes in the preparatory periods helps to increase the calculated value of maximum anaerobic power by an average of 7-9% [2, 10, 11]. When running short distances, along with functional readiness, special importance is attached to the level of technical skill of the athlete. To successfully improve running technique, it is not enough to imagine only the external form of movements; you need to know their quantitative and qualitative properties [3].

Knowledge of the characteristics of the motor structure of running, as well as its changes under the influence of fatigue at the end of the distance, can serve as a scientific basis for the selection of means for effective technical training of young short-distance runners. Research by scientists and practitioners indicates that there is a pattern of changes in 200 and 400 m running technique under the influence of fatigue in athletes specializing in short-distance running [9, 12].

A number of experiments have proven the effectiveness of using special exercises, taking into account the most significant changes in running technique under the influence of fatigue. The use of this technique in the educational and training process for young men, taking into account the peculiarities of running technique at the end of the distance, makes it possible to reduce speed losses and significantly improve results in 200 m and 400 m running [13].

Consequently, it is possible to increase the efficiency of the process of training athletes in the conditions of study at a higher educational institution by using special exercises in the training process, their diversity and an individual approach to students of various specializations. Increasing the effect of such exercises requires their constant use throughout the entire training period.

The physical training of a short-distance runner, like any athlete, is divided into general and special. The functional potential acquired by an athlete in the process of general physical training is only a necessary condition for successful improvement in sports, but cannot ensure the achievement of high sports results without targeted special physical training [15, 17].

The level of results in modern sports, in particular sprinting, is very high. In sprint sports, the volumes and intensity of training and competitive loads performed by the athlete have reached their maximum permissible limit. Consequently, further improvement of sports results is impossible without a scientific approach to organizing the training process [18, 19].

An analysis of scientific and methodological literature indicates that short-distance running was studied by many scientists who studied the physical and technical readiness of track and field sprinters and the means of improving them in the training process [1, 4, 7]. The structure of the physical and technical readiness of short-distance runners has been partially studied by researchers of elite sports, but at the stage of specialized basic training, athletes cannot use it.

An increase in sports results is possible only with a harmonious relationship between all aspects of preparedness. In the practice of training athletes, phenomena are sometimes observed when contradictions arise between the growing level of physical qualities and technique in that motor skills, learned and consolidated at a certain level, subsequently have a restraining effect in their implementation [12, 13].

Daniyeva Ya. Ch. in her work determined that the level of special physical fitness of sprinters of various qualifications is most fully reflected by the results of such indicators: running 30 and 60 m from a low start, standing long jump, standing triple

jump and strength of flexors and extensors thighs, legs. The use of weights allows athletes to exceed the limit of “critical” amounts of effort power that develop when working under normal conditions. The art of the teacher is to determine these maximum stimuli individually for each student, without creating conditions for overexertion. Studies have shown the effectiveness of using the following types of weights: a belt weighing 4-8% of the leg weight, a bag weighing 15-25% of the body weight [11].

Research shows that recently the level of physical fitness in sports schools has decreased compared to the past [14, 15, 16]. First of all, this negative trend is associated with outdated or monotonous methods of physical training. In addition, the problem of improving the special physical fitness of sprint runners requires further development and clarification. All this determines the position of scientific novelty, relevance and practical significance of the study. Consequently, the purpose of our work is to study the characteristics of special physical training of short-distance runners. The objectives of our research: to study and summarize the scientific and methodological literature on the features of special physical training of sprinters.

As a result of studying special literature, the main physical qualities that most influence the special physical training of short-distance runners have been established. Namely, explosive power can be a decisive factor when performing the old woman in runners; speed strength has a decisive influence on athletic performance in short-distance running; maximum strength largely determines the athletic performance of sprinters; complex manifestations of speed, ensuring the ability to achieve a high level of speed over a distance, the ability to gain speed at the start in a short time.

Conclusions. Analysis of scientific and methodological literature shows that the success of training athletes in modern conditions depends on the effectiveness of methods of organization, management and control, rational use of modern technologies in the training process, taking into account the individual, age,

psychological and morphofunctional characteristics of the body. Training with additional weights contributes to the development of special physical fitness of athletes, which in turn increases the results of short-distance runners.

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